

Hydrolysis of Di-*p*-chlorophenylphosphate

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The acid catalysed hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate has been found to proceed via conjugate acid, neutral and mononegative species, with a rate maxima at 2.43 M perchloric acid. Ionic strength effect data permits the separation of acid catalysed and neutral rates but the calculated rates using the data do not agree with experimental rates, however, experimental rates for mononegative species agree well with those of calculated rates determined from assumed pK values. Solvent isotope effect and Arrhenius parameters show the reaction to be bimolecular.

HYDROLYSIS of mono phosphate esters has been found to proceed via mononegative, neutral and conjugate acid species with a rate maxima at pH 4. Mono esters with electron attracting groups show acid catalysis¹⁻³. catalysed hydrolysis of diphenyl and dimethyl^{1,4,5,6} phosphates involve phosphorus-oxygen bond fission. In the present investigation hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate has been studied with a view to know its behaviour towards acid catalysis and results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate was prepared from *p*-chloro phenol and phosphorus oxychloride and purified by recrystallization^{2,3}

m.p. observed ... 124°
reported ... 126°

Procedure: The hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate (0.001M) was followed by colorimetric determination of inorganic phosphate by Allen's method⁷. Buffer solutions for kinetic experiments were used for which pH values have been given at 20° and 150° by Stene⁸ and interpolated values of these buffer solutions at intermediate temperatures were used⁵. Constant ionic strength was maintained with sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid⁵.

Deuterium oxide of isotopic purity >99.4% was procured from B.A.R.C., Trombay. All the chemicals used in present work were of A.R. grade.

Calculations: The first order rate coefficients for the hydrolysis of diester were calculated using equation^{4,6}:

$$K_D = \frac{2.303}{t} \cdot \log \frac{D}{D - (M + P)}$$

where K_D , D , M , P and t are the first order rate coefficients, concentrations of diester, monoster, inorganic phosphate and time respectively. Concentration of monoester was determined as:

$$M = \frac{d_p}{d_t} \times \frac{1}{K_M}$$

where K_M is rate of monoester².

Results and Discussion

Hydrolysis of conjugate acid species: The hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate has been studied in the range 0.4 to 7 M perchloric acid with a rate maxima at approximately 2.5 M perchloric acid as observed in other diesters^{4,5} and then the rates decrease (Figure 1). Plots of log rates against log CH^+ give unit slope (up to 2.43M) which indicates that reaction is bimolecular i.e. it involves a nucleophilic attack of water molecule⁹. Ionic strength effect has been studied at constant ionic strength (2 and 3 μ) and results indicate

Fig. 1. Hydrolysis of Di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate in the range pH 6.43 to 7 M perchloric acid at 80°

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TABLE 1—HYDROLYSIS OF DI-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT CONSTANT IONIC STRENGTH* AT 80°

	$\mu=2$			
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
HClO ₄ 10 ⁴ Kmin ⁻¹	17.22	26.45	27.54	31.91
	$\mu=3$			
	1.5	2.0	2.5	
HClO ₄ 10 ⁴ Kmin ⁻¹	35.5	37.5	47.79	

*Constant Ionic strength being maintained with sodium perchlorate

that reaction is acid catalysed and subject to positive salt effect² (Table 1). The lines meet at one point on rate axis which shows that neutral species also contribute towards the reaction, though their contribution being small and constant. The hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate can be represented as² :

$$k_e = K_{No} + K_{Ho} \cdot b \mu H^+ \quad \dots (1)$$

where K_e , K_{No} , K_{Ho} , b and μ are the observed rate, specific neutral and specific acid catalysed rate at zero ionic strength, a constant and ionic strength respectively. Using above equation the acid catalysed rates can be calculated as :

$$K_e = 4.16 + 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1} (K_{Ho}) \cdot 0.12 (b) \mu H^+ \cdot a H_2O \quad \dots (ii)$$

(contribution from neutral species being constant and is $0.25 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$.)

The sum of acid catalysed and neutral rates do not agree with experimental rates even though the activity of water is included in equation¹⁰. Solvent isotope effect ($K_{D_2O}/K_{H_2O} < 1$) indicates a slow proton transfer⁹. Arrhenius parameters (entropy of activation = -65.0 e. u and $E = 10.59 \text{ K.cal/mole}$) favour bimolecular nature of reaction¹¹. As with other phosphate esters^{2,3}, hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate may be presumed to proceed via phosphorus-oxygen bond fission and probable mechanism consistent with available kinetic data may be formulated as :

*R = *p*-chlorophenyl

Hydrolysis of mononegative species : The hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate has been studied in buffers in the range pH 1.24 to 6.43 at 80° (Table 2 and Figure 1). The hydrolysis proceeds via mononegative and neutral species. The rates of hydrolysis rise slowly with maximum at pH 6.43 as observed in diphenyl phosphate^{1,4}. The hydrolysis in the range pH 1.24 to 6.43 is governed by mononegative and neutral species and can be represented as^{2,8} :

TABLE 2—RATES OF HYDROLYSIS OF DI-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL PHOSPHATE AT 80°

pH	N/N+M	M/M+N	10 ⁴ K, min ⁻¹	
			Calculated.	Observed.
1.24	0.99	0.01	2.25	2.157
2.22	0.946	0.05	2.29	2.278
3.33	0.638	0.36	2.65	3.084
4.17	0.150	0.85	3.22	3.039
5.60	0.017	0.98	3.38	3.681
6.43	0.001	0.998	3.41	3.980

$$K_e = K_M \cdot \frac{M}{M+N} + K_N \cdot \frac{N}{N+M} \quad \dots (iii)$$

where K_e , K_M , K_N , $M/M+N$, $N/M+N$ are the observed rate coefficients of monoanions at that acidity, specific rate coefficient of monoanion and neutral species respectively. K_M has been presumed to be observed rate ($3.98 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$.) at pH 6.43 where $M/M+N$ is approximately unity. Fraction of mononegative and neutral species have been calculated from assumed pK value of 3.25 at 80°,^{2,3} (Table 2). The slope and plots of rates against fractions of mononegative species also give K_M and K_N as $3.407 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$. and $2.08 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$. respectively. As the fraction of neutral species is almost unity at pH 1.24, K_N has been taken as observed rates at that pH ($2.16 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$.). K_N from ionic strength data comes to be $2.5 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$.) Mean value of $K_N = 2.24 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$.) Thus the calculated rates for hydrolysis in the range pH 1.24 to 6.43 using equation (iii) agree well with experimental rates (Table 2). Arrhenius parameters (entropy of activation = -64.74 e. u. and $E = 7.4 \text{ K.cal/mole}$) are also in favour of bimolecular reaction. The hydrolysis of di-*p*-chlorophenyl phosphate may be taken to involve phosphorus-oxygen bond fission as observed in the hydrolysis of diphenyl phosphate and probable mechanism for the hydrolysis of mononegative and neutral species may be formulated as :

HYDROLYSIS OF NEUTRAL SPECIES

HYDROLYSIS OF MONONEGATIVE SPECIES

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